

Electrochemistry of Fluoride Solutions. Part VII. Electrodeposition of Cobalt from Fluoride Solutions

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The electrodeposition of cobalt from acid fluoride solutions has been studied. The decomposition and discharge potentials and anodic dissolution potential of cobalt in the acid solutions have been determined. The nature of the deposits from solutions of different compositions and the effect of addition agents on deposits have been studied. Thiourea has been proved to be the most beneficial addition agent. The optimum conditions for the deposition of very fine, lustrous, smooth, ductile, adherent, and non-porous deposits have been determined. The bath described in the paper is to be regarded as one of the very best for the deposition of the metal.

Gore¹ reported that a black powder was deposited on the cathode when a solution of cobalt fluoride was electrolysed. Smith² employed an ammoniacal fluoride solution for separating cobalt from nickel. Edmister and Cooper³ used a similar solution for the electrolytic estimation of cobalt. No other reference is to be found in literature to a straight forward electrolysis of cobalt fluoride solutions with particular reference to cathodic reactions. A large volume of data has, however, been gathered by numerous workers on the use of alkali, ammonium, or hydrogen fluoride, either singly or in combinations, as addition agents to other cobalt baths. The present investigation was undertaken with the object of gaining information on the possibility of utilising either neutral or acid cobalt fluoride solutions for the electrolytic deposition of the metal for protective purposes. Detailed data have been obtained on (a) decomposition and discharge potentials of cobalt fluoride in neutral and acid solutions as well as the dissolution potential of cobalt in the latter, (b) nature of the cobalt deposits on platinum and copper cathodes under diverse conditions, (c) porosity of deposits obtained, and (d) throwing power of selected acid fluoride baths.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt fluoride solutions were prepared in the same way as in the case of nickel solutions⁴. The amount of cobalt in solution was determined by the cyanide method, recommended by Evans⁵, based on the quantitative oxidation of cobalt in alkaline (cyanide) solutions by passage of air and back titration of the excess cyanide with silver nitrate.

Preliminary trials with mixtures containing known amounts of cobalt sulphate and hydrofluoric acid showed that, even with a ratio of hydrofluoric acid to cobalt as high as 56, the method was quite accurate.

1. "Electrochemistry", *The Electrician*, London, 1906, p. 90.
2. *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1915, 27, 33.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2419.
4. Kappanna and Talaty, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 663.
5. *J. Electrodep. Tech. Soc.*, 1938, 14, 141.

The cyanide solution was standardised against recrystallised Merck's C. P. grade cobalt sulphate. The amount of unneutralised hydrofluoric acid in the solutions prepared could be calculated as in the case of nickel⁴.

Porosity Tests.—The tests were performed, as in the case of nickel⁴, by the ferroxyl test using $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ instead of the usual ferricyanide.

DISCUSSION

Decomposition, Discharge, and Dissolution Potentials

The decomposition and discharge potentials of cobalt fluoride in both neutral and acid solutions were measured at 30°, using polished platinum electrodes. These measurements were also made in an acid solution containing thiourea, as this substance gave the best deposits of cobalt in the present investigation. These results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

In acid cobalt fluoride solutions.

Temperature=30°. Electrodes: polished platinum.

No.	Solution composition.	Voltage between electrodes.		Discharge potentials (E_h).			Dissolution potential of cobalt (E_h).	
		1st break.	2nd break (decomp. potential).	Cathode 1st break.	potential 2nd break.	Anode potential.	1st break.	2nd break.
1	0.1960M-CoF ₂ , 0.3998M-HF	1.46	1.90	0.06	-0.34	1.52	-0.05	3.80
2	0.0705M-CoF ₂ , 0.1712M-HF	1.41	1.89	0.04	-0.39	1.45	..	..
3	0.1216M-CoF ₂ , 0.6224M-HF	1.42	1.80	0.05	-0.30	1.43	..	..
4	0.1216M-CoF ₂ , 0.6224M-HF, Thiourea (2.510 g./litre)	0.55	0.99	-0.04	-0.47	0.50	..	..
5	0.0478M-CoF ₂	1.04	2.34	-0.02	-1.02	1.20	..	..
6	0.0478M-CoF ₂	1.71	2.26	0.04	-0.40	1.75	..	..

The discharge potential measurements were made with reference to a saturated calomel electrode and the values reduced to the hydrogen scale.

The current density—cathode potential and the current density—applied voltage curves showed two breaks, the first one due to deposition of a trace of copper present in the hydrofluoric acid used and the second one due to the deposition of cobalt (Figs. 1 and 2).

FIG 1

FIG. 2

The difference between the discharge potentials of the two metals was again sufficiently great (about 0.4 volt in acid solutions and 1.0 volt in the neutral solution) to show promise of a quantitative separation of copper and cobalt in fluoride solutions. As in the case of nickel⁴, the discharge potentials of cobalt are more negative than those to be expected from the normal electrode potential of cobalt (0.28 volt on the hydrogen scale) at the dilutions prevailing in these experiments, but the values in acid fluoride solutions are seen to be much closer to the reversible value than those in sulphate solutions, which is again a point in favour of acid fluoride baths. In a neutral fluoride bath, considerable polarisation was, however, present.

The anode discharge potentials, on the other hand, were generally much different from those found in the case of nickel fluoride solutions. This is because a black substance begins to be deposited at the platinum anode at potentials corresponding to the break points in the current density—*anode potential* curves. The actual discharge potentials varied considerably with the composition and strength of the solution. These results and the composition of the anodic product ($\text{Co}_3\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and the mechanism of its formation have been discussed by us in a previous communication⁶.

FIG. 3

The anodic dissolution of cobalt in an acid fluoride solution has also been studied; the current density—*anode potential* curve is shown in Fig. 3. It will be seen that the curve is similar to that obtained in the case of nickel⁴ with this difference that the polarisation is less and the potential at the second break, at which oxygen-evolution commences, is much higher than that for nickel. This is in conformity with the behaviour of cobalt in other solutions. The most noteworthy point, however, is the continuous

dissolution of cobalt, even at higher current densities when oxygen is evolved at the same time. This is definitely another point in favour of fluoride solutions.

Electrodeposition of Cobalt

The experiments were conducted at room temperature (30-32°) with agitation of the electrolytes. Platinum cathodes were employed in the first instance in all the baths; later on, deposits were obtained on copper cathodes to study their nature and porosity. The anode used was a plate of pure cobalt metal and the current density at the anode was always half of that at the cathode. The duration of each run was usually 1 hour.

Preliminary experiments showed that neutral fluoride solutions or those having a high proportion of free hydrofluoric acid provided unsatisfactory, dark, and loose deposits. As a result of a large number of trials, the following composition was found to furnish reasonably good and lustrous deposits: 0.1216*M* cobalt fluoride and 0.6229 *M*-HF. All further work was carried out with this bath, a current density of 3.0 amp./dm² being employed.

Addition of ammonium fluoride in small quantities improved the deposit a little, but not to the desirable extent. Similarly, addition of sodium and potassium carbonates could not push the improvement very much further. Influence of the following addition agents on the nature of deposits was investigated in detail: peptone, glucose, naphthalene- β -sulphonic acid, brucine, hydrogen peroxide, gelatin, thiourea. Most of these exerted some beneficial effect. Naphthalene- β sulphonic acid, however, brought about some deterioration. Thiourea proved to be the most beneficial addition agent.

The optimum concentration of thiourea in the bath was found to be 2.51 g./litre. The deposit obtained on copper under these conditions with thiourea happens to be much better than deposits obtained from any other cobalt bath within the experience of the authors. The details of the findings are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Addition of thiourea.

Original solution: 0.1216*M*-CoF₂, 0.6224*M*-HF.

Average cathode current density=3.0 amp./dm².

No.	Thiourea (g./litre).	Applied voltage.	Cathode current efficiency.	Nature of deposit.
1	0.0800	2.6	66.38%	Deposit was more lustrous and smoother than that produced without the addition of thiourea.
2	0.9133	2.4	68.14	Throwing power of the solution was a little better than that in (1); otherwise, the deposit was of the same nature as (1). Anode became black in appearance.
2(a)	„	2.3	71.04	Deposit on a copper cathode was white, lustrous, and very ductile, but slightly pitted. A few nodules were formed at the edges. Throwing power of the solution was fairly good.

TABLE II (contd.)

No.	Thiourea (g./litre).	Applied voltage.	Cathode current efficiency.	Nature of deposit.
3	2.5100	2.2	69.12	Deposit was more white, smoother and more lustrous than (2). Pitting was almost absent. Throwing power of the solution was somewhat better than that in (2).
3(a)	2.5100	2.1	72.52	Deposit on a copper cathode was lustrous, very ductile, and free from pits. Throwing power of the solution was quite good. Anode current efficiency=122.23%.
3(b)	2.5100	1.0	70.89	Expt. 3(a) was repeated at a lower current density, namely, 2.0 amp./dm ² . There were now no nodules at the edges of the deposit, but throwing power of the solution was a little less than that in 3(a).
4	7.0847	2.3	62.20	The deposit was slightly darker than (3) and nodule-formation at the edges increased.
5	12.3660	2.3	57.25	Bigger nodules were formed at the edges; otherwise, the deposit was of the same nature as (4).
6	25.6913	2.4	55.70	Same as (5).
7	40.3700	2.5	56.64	A dull, dark, 'treed', and somewhat pitted deposit was formed.

Thiourea also lowered the bath voltage and thus proved to be further advantageous. Current-potential measurements show (Fig. 2) that this lowering of bath voltage is due to a tremendous lowering in the anode-discharge potential, which appears to be due to secondary reactions setting in on the anode, as no cobaltic oxide formation takes place on a platinum anode in presence of thiourea. The cathode-discharge potential, however, increased. The throwing power of the bath with thiourea was measured in a Haring and Blum box as this addition agent gave deposits which were very ductile, smooth, lustrous, non-porous, and highly satisfactory. For comparison, the throwing power of the bath without thiourea was also measured. The values are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Throwing power of acid cobalt fluoride baths.

Temp.=30°. Average cathode-current density=3.0 amp./dm².

No.	Solution composition.	Throwing power.	
		Platinum cathode.	Copper cathode.
1	0.1216M-CoF ₂ , 0.6224M-HF	-7.08%	3.20%
2	0.1216M-CoF ₂ , 0.6224M-HF, thiourea (2.5100 g./litre)	31.48	43.22

The improvement in the throwing power is to be expected from the increase in cathodic polarisation caused by thiourea as also from a smaller variation in cathode-current efficiency with current density observed in presence of thiourea.

The composition and operating conditions of the bath affording very highly satisfactory deposits are given below:

Solution composition :	0.1216M-CoF ₂ , 0.6224M-HF; thiourea, 2.51g./litre.
Cathode-current density:-	3.0 amp./dm ² with agitation of electrolyte.
Anode " " :	1.5 amp./dm ² (cobalt anode).
Applied potential:	2.1 volts.
Temperature:	30°.
Cathode-current efficiency:	72.52%.
Anode " " :	122.23%.

The high anode-current efficiency (above 100%) is obviously due to the corrosive action of hydrofluoric acid on freshly exposed surface of cobalt during anodic dissolution.

In conclusion it should be stated that the bath described above is amongst the very best for deposition of cobalt.

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